

Fracture Behavior of SiC Whisker Reinforced Aluminum Alloy under Combined Tension/Torsion Loading at Room and Elevated Temperatures

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an investigation on the quasi-static and fatigue fracture behavior of an SiC whisker reinforced A6061 aluminum alloy fabricated by a squeeze casting process under combined tension/torsion loading at room and elevated temperatures. The tests were conducted keeping a constant value of the combined stress ratio, $\alpha = \tau/\sigma$. Except for the elongation at failure, mechanical properties of the composite including fatigue strength were superior to those of an unreinforced A6061 alloy, not only under uniaxial loading, but also under combined tension/torsion loading. Fracture surfaces were closely examined, and the fracture mechanisms under combined tension/torsion loading were discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous progress in science and technology creates increasing demand for further improved structural materials; the mechanical properties required in many technological fields are high-strength, low-specific density, high wear resistance, and also heat-resistant property. Of various structural materials, metal matrix composites have attracted engineers and researchers because of their potentials to meet such demands. Especially short fiber such as whisker reinforced metals [1] are easy for machining compared to continuous fiber reinforced metals. Many researches have been performed on strengthening mechanisms [2], fracture [2, 3] and fatigue [5-7] behavior, and also environmental influences on fracture [5, 8]. However, fracture behavior at elevated temperature [9-11], including fatigue in multi-axial loading conditions, are scarcely reported, although it is important from the standpoints of the application of a composite to machines and structures.

In this investigation, the authors have conducted quasi-static and fatigue tests of an SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloy under combined tension/torsion loading at room and elevated temperatures. Fracture surfaces were closely examined with scanning electron microscopes, and the fracture mechanisms of the composite are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The material tested was an SiC whisker reinforced A6061 aluminum alloy ($V_f = 22\%$). The composite, which was heat-treated to a T6 condition, was fabricated through a squeeze casting process, with final extrusion rate of 28, and thus most whisker aligned in the longitudinal direction: some whisker rich and poor zones could be observed in microscopic order, although no whisker clusters existed. The diameter of the whisker ranged from $0.3\mu\text{m}$ to $2\mu\text{m}$, giving an average diameter of $1\mu\text{m}$; the length of the whisker after the processing was $2 - 7\mu\text{m}$, with an average of about $4\mu\text{m}$.

Smooth specimens shown in Fig. 1 were machined in the longitudinal direction, i.e., extruding direction. The specimens were polished with emery papers (#1500) followed with final finish with a dia-

mond paste. The testing machine employed was electro-hydraulic servo-controlled tension-torsion fatigue testing machine (load capacity: $\pm 100\text{kN}$, $\pm 1\text{kN}\cdot\text{m}$). Tests were conducted at room and elevated temperatures of 200°C and 300°C . Elevated temperature was achieved with an infrared heating apparatus at an increasing temperature rate of 0.5°C/s from room temperature. Temperature of a specimen was measured with a chromel-alumel thermocouple, which was adhered to the specimen. Tests were conducted after a specimen had been held at elevated temperature for 30 minutes.

Fig.1 Shape and dimensions of specimens.

Static and fatigue tests under in-phase combined tension/torsion loading were conducted for both composite and unreinforced matrix material, under a load-controlled condition keeping a constant value of a combined stress ratio, $\alpha = \tau/\sigma$, where σ is the axial stress and τ the torsional stress. Changing combined stress ratio, fatigue tests at a stress ratio of 0.1 were performed at a frequency of 1Hz at room temperature and at 2Hz at 200°C . Fracture surfaces were closely examined with scanning electron microscopes (HFS-2 by Hitachi, and JSM-5400LV by JEOL).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

QUASI-STATIC FRACTURE BEHAVIOR

Table 1 summarizes the mechanical properties at room and elevated temperature under uniaxial tension ($\alpha=0$). Figure 2 shows the static strengths under in-phase combined loading, which are plotted in relation of axial stress and torsional stress. The arrows in the figure indicate that specimens did not completely fractured even though the maximum torsional angle (about ± 50 degrees) was applied to the specimen.

The static strengths of the composite at room and elevated temperatures were superior to those of an unreinforced A6061 alloy, not only under uniaxial loading, but also under combined tension/torsion loading. This increase in strength was more pronounced at room temperature. However, elongation at break decreased by the reinforcement (Table 1), giving a brittle nature to the composite. The solid lines shown in Fig.2 are the predicted failure strengths by Tsai-Hill failure criterion, derived by tensile ($\alpha=0$) and torsional ($\alpha=\infty$) strengths: the static strength of both composite and unreinforced matrix material showed good agreement with the Tsai-Hill failure criterion, indicating that the strength was determined by this criterion.

Figure 3 shows the normalized strength as a function of testing temperature, where the strength was divided by the room temperature strength. At higher α levels, a decrease in strength of the composite with an increase in temperature showed similar tendency as the matrix material.

Fig.2 Quasi-static strength under tension/torsion combined loading.

Table 1(a) Mechanical properties of $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6061}$ under uniaxial tension.

Temperature	Tensile Strength, MPa	Elongation at Break, %	Elastic Modulus, GPa
RT	574	4.7	118
200°C	312	19.5	---
300°C	164	26.5	---

Table 1(b) Mechanical properties of A6061 Al alloy under uniaxial tension.

Temperature	Tensile Strength, MPa	Elongation at Break, %	Elastic Modulus, GPa
RT	329	10.6	72.4
200°C	250	52.1	---
300°C	103	≥ 62	---

(a) SiC_w/A6061

(b) A6061 Al alloy

Fig.3 Normalized strength as a function of temperature

However, at lower α levels, there was a linear relation between composite strength and testing temperature.

In the case of discontinuous fiber composite, basic strengthening mechanisms which are considered are [2]:

- (1) High dislocation density due to dislocation generation by mismatch of coefficient of thermal expansion of the reinforcement and matrix material.
- (2) Small subgrain sizes by high dislocation density
- (3) Residual stress
- (4) Classical load transfer mechanisms
- (5) Dispersion hardening

Of these, high-dislocation density is recently considered to play an important roll in strengthening mechanism [2, 13, 14]. Interfacial strength of SiC whisker and aluminum matrix is so high that it is reasonable to approximate the interfacial strength as half as yielding strength of the matrix material (=149MPa). Considering the whisker strength (5.9-19.6 MPa) [19], the critical aspect ratio was obtained at 20-60, which was larger than the aspect ratio of the whisker of this composite system. Therefore, the simplest strengthening model of the Kelly-Tyson equation could be applied, giving the composite strength 450 MPa, under uniaxial loading. This was smaller than the experimental value of 574 MPa, suggesting that classical composite strengthening mechanism of load transfer could not be applied to this composite system: other strengthening mechanism such as a dislocation model proposed by Arsenault [2, 13, 14] must be considered.

At elevated temperature, however, an increase of strength by the reinforcement decreased, and the experimental strength showed almost the similar value as predicted by the classical load transfer model. At elevated temperature, recrystallization of the matrix material was promoted, and this suppressed the strengthening mechanisms, which worked effectively at room temperature.

FRACTURE SURFACE MORPHOLOGY UNDER QUASI-STATIC LOADING

Fracture Surface under Uniaxial Tension

Fracture surface of the composite was of cup and cone type, showing radial marking: this indicated that crack initiation site was inside of a specimen. The macroscopic fracture morphology of the unreinforced matrix material was similar to that of the composite, except larger yielding behavior.

(a) Alumina inclusion

(b) Voids and precipitates (Arrows: facets of precipitate; "A": voids)

Fig.4 Crack initiation site of SiC_w/A6061 under quasi-static, uniaxial tension (room temperature, $\alpha = 0$)

However, crack initiation site could not be confirmed.

Figure 4 shows the SEM photographs of the crack initiation site of the composite: a crack initiated at an inclusion with a diameter of 50-60 μm (Fig.4(a)), a void, and facet of a precipitate (Fig.4(b)). EPMA analysis proved that the inclusion was Al_2O_3 . This was introduced during fabrication process of preforms. Micro-voids shown in Fig. 4(b) were about 5 μm in diameter, and were frequently observed on the fracture surface, irrespective of testing condition. At crack growing stage of the composite, the matrix material failed in a ductile manner around each whisker, and formed dimples around whisker (Fig.5(a)): dimple size was almost equaled the distance between each whisker. The precipitate facet could be observed (Fig.5(b)). The EPMA analysis showed that the precipitate consisted of Fe, Al, and Si [16, 17]. In the case of matrix material, dimple failures dominated, although the size of dimple was still larger than the composite.

At elevated temperature, macroscopic fracture morphology was the same as that at room temperature, although it was difficult to confirm the initiation site: no radial marking was observed, unlike at room temperature. For the composite at elevated temperature, several cracks initiated at micro-voids with diameter of about 5 μm , and these crack coalesced each other, leading to final failure. This is the reason why it was difficult to confirm the crack initiation site. A dimple size of the composite and matrix material became larger at elevated temperature: see Fig.5(c). For the composite, multiple whiskers could be sometimes observed in a bottom of a single dimple.

Figure 6 shows the dimple depth as a function of testing temperature. From the figures, dimple depth of the composite and matrix material increased with increasing testing temperature, although the depth of the matrix material was still larger than that of the composite. In other words, dimple depth increased with an increase in elongation at break or ductility of the material. By applying an image processing technique to reconstruct three-dimensional shapes of chary impacted fracture surfaces of steels, the authors already reported that, dimple size or fracture surface area ratio increased with testing temperature, and this agreed with an increased absorbed energy, i.e., higher ductility [18]. The same results could be obtained for the whisker reinforced composite.

Fracture Surface under Tension/Torsion Loading

Under combined tension/torsion loading, the maximum stress is always on the specimen surface, and hence the crack initiation site, precipitates or voids, was always on the specimen surface. A crack that led final failure was on a plane where the maximum shear stress existed, forming a spiral crack around the specimen (Fig.7). Near the crack initiation site, elongated dimples were observed, and some whisker pull-out existed (Fig.8).

At elevated temperature, multiple cracks were observed, unlike at room temperature. The crack direction did not necessarily agreed with that of the maximum shear stress. Fracture surface was covered with dimples, and their size increased with an increase in testing temperature. A crack initiation site was hard to be confirmed because the fracture surfaces rubbed each other.

(a) Dimples (room temperature)

(b) Facets of precipitate (room temperature)

(c) Dimples (300°C)

Fig.5 Quasi-static fracture surface of $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6061}$ under uniaxial tension ($\alpha = 0$).

(a) SiC_w/A6061

(b) A6061 Al alloy

Fig.6 Dimple depth as a function of temperature

Fig.7 Macroscopic fracture morphology of a quasi-static test of SiC_w/A6061 under tension/torsion loading (room temperature, $\alpha=1$)

Fig.8 Quasi-static fracture surface of SiC_w/A6061 under tension/torsion loading (Room temperature, $\alpha=0.5$, Arrows: whisker pull-out)

FRACTURE MECHANISM UNDER QUASI-STATIC LOADING

At room and elevated temperatures, crack initiation sites of the composite were precipitates or voids in the matrix. At relatively low stress level compared with the tensile strength, a crack initiated at large precipitates in the matrix. However, the ductility of the matrix material was high, and the crack did not continue to grow; local slip zone ahead of the crack was alternately formed. As was shown before, the dimple size was in the order of whisker distance. This suggested that micro-voids were generated at whisker end due to stress concentration or by whisker breakage. They coalesced each other, leading to final failure of the composite, resulting in dimples and facets of precipitates. This meant that the strength of the composite could be increased if the defects including relatively large inclusions or voids were suppressed.

FATIGUE FRACTURE BEHAVIOR

Figures 9 and 10 show S-N curves at room and elevated temperatures (200°C), plotted against maximum principal and equivalent stress. Irrespective of testing temperature, the fatigue strength at $\alpha \leq 1$ was determined by maximum principal stress, whereas the strength at $\alpha \geq 2$ by equivalent stress. Moreover, the fatigue strength of the composite at higher stress levels was higher than that of unreinforced matrix material not only under uniaxial tension but also under combined tension/torsion loading. However, at lower stress levels, an increase of fatigue strength by whisker reinforcement became smaller.

FATIGUE FRACTURE SURFACE

Fracture Surface under Uniaxial Tension

For the composite at room temperature, surface and inside crack initiation sites were observed. When an initiation site was inside of a specimen, the crack initiated at a precipitate, and it grew and formed conical fracture surface (Fig. 11). The base line of this cone was about 49 degrees against the longitudi-

(a) Relation between maximum principal stress and number of cycles to fracture.

(b) Relation between maximum equivalent stress and number of cycles to fracture.

Fig.9 S-N curves (Room temperature)

(a) Relation between maximum principal stress and number of cycles to fracture.

(b) Relation between maximum equivalent stress and number of cycles to fracture.

Fig.10 S-N curves (200°C)

(a) Top view

(b) Side view of Fig.11(a)

Fig.11 Inside fatigue crack initiation site under uniaxial tension (room temperature, $\alpha=0$)

nal direction. This conical fracture surface was more often observed at 200°C: cracks initiated at a voids of about 5 - 10 μm in size, which was due to insufficient infiltration of the matrix material (Fig. 12(b)), and the final fracture was caused by coalescence of these cracks, forming multiple cones on the fracture surface (Fig. 12(a)). For surface crack initiation site, whisker pull-outs were observed at the initiation sites, similarly to SiC_w/7075, which was reported elsewhere [5].

(a) Low magnification photograph (arrows: initiation sites)

(b) High-magnification crack initiation site (void)

Fig.12 Fatigue crack initiation site under uniaxial tension (200°C, $\alpha = 0$)

Fig.13 Fatigue crack initiation site under tension/torsion loading of $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6061}$ (room temperature, $\alpha = 1$, $\sigma_{\max} = 245\text{MPa}$, $N_f = 1.39 \times 10^5$, arrows: whisker pull-out, "A": void)

Fig.14 Fatigue fracture surface under tension/torsion loading of $\text{SiC}_w/\text{A6061}$ (room temperature, $\alpha = 0.5$, $\sigma_{\max} = 408\text{MPa}$, $N_f = 1.39 \times 10^4$)

Near an initiation site, neither dimples around whisker nor whisker was observed: a crack mainly propagated in the matrix, with zig-zag path avoiding whisker. However, no striation existed, which was observed in the unreinforced matrix material. With crack extension, crack path became straight, and dimples around each whisker dominated over the fracture surface at final fracture stage, like the case of quasi-static loading tests.

Fracture Surface under Combined Tension/Torsion Loading

At room temperature, a crack on a plane, where the maximum shear stress existed, led final failure. As was discussed before, the fatigue strength at $\alpha \leq 1$ was determined by maximum principal stress, and it suggested that the dominating mechanism of crack initiation and crack propagation was different, and further investigations are necessary.

Similarly to quasi-static tests, a crack always initiated at the surface site. However, morphology of the initiation site was dependent on fatigue lives. At lower $N_f (\leq 10^5)$, a crack initiated at defects such as voids introduced by insufficient infiltration of the matrix material; at longer $N_f (> 10^5)$, whisker pull-out could be seen near the initiation site of a void (Fig.13).

Near an initiation site, whisker was scarcely observed, and a crack mainly propagated in the matrix,

with zig-zag path (Fig.14). With the crack extension, however, whisker pull-out and whisker breakage were observed, and finally, dimples dominated over the surface.

At elevated temperature, no whisker pull-out existed, which was observed near the initiation site at room temperature: multiple cracks were observed on the specimen surface. This was consistent with the results of quasi-static tests. At the crack propagation stage, details of fracture surface morphology was unclear because the fracture surfaces rubbed each other. With crack extension, dimples became dominant, and oxides induced by fretting could be observed.

CONCLUSIONS

Quasi-static and fatigue tests of an SiC whisker reinforced A6061 aluminum alloy under in-phase combined tension/torsion loading at room and elevated temperatures were performed. This investigation yielded the following conclusions:

1. The quasi-static strength of the composite under combined tension/torsion loading was superior to that of unreinforced matrix material. An increase in strength at room temperature was more pronounced at lower α levels. At elevated temperature, however, an increase of strength at lower α levels was small.
2. The Thai-Hill failure criterion determined quasi-static strength of both composite and unreinforced matrix material at room and elevated temperatures.
3. For quasi-static tests, a crack initiated at facets of a large precipitate or voids introduced by insufficient matrix infiltration: the strength would be improved, if such defects could be suppressed.
4. Fatigue strength of the composite under combined tension/torsion loading was superior to that of unreinforced matrix material, irrespective of testing temperature. An increase in fatigue strength was in particular high at higher stress levels; at lower stress levels, an increase of fatigue strength by whisker reinforcement became smaller.
5. The fatigue strength at $\alpha \leq 1$ was determined by maximum principal stress, whereas the strength at $\alpha \geq 2$ by equivalent stress.

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